

EFFECT OF FARTLEK TRAINING ON SELECTED PHYSICAL VARIABLES AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of fartlek training on selected physical variables among college students. In this study, 30 students from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given experimental treatment. The fartlek training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14. It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement on selected physical variables.

Key Words: Fartlek Training, Speed, Agility.

Introduction:

Fartlek means "speed play" in Swedish, is a training method that blends continuous training with interval training. The variable intensity and continuous nature of the exercise places stress on both the aerobic and anaerobic systems. It differs from traditional interval training in that it is unstructured; intensity and/or speed varies, as the athlete wishes. Most fartlek sessions last a minimum of 45 minutes and can vary from aerobic walking to anaerobic sprinting. Fartlek training is generally associated with running, but can include almost any kind of exercise. Swedish coach Gosta Holmer developed fartlek in 1937, and, since then, many physiologists have adopted it. It was designed for the downtrodden Swedish cross country running teams that had been beaten throughout the 1920s by Paavo Nurmi and the Finns. Holmer’s plan used a faster-than-race pace and concentrated on both speed and endurance training (Antony et al. 2019).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of fartlek training on selected physical variables among college students. In this study, 30 students from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given experimental treatment. The fartlek training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14.

Results:

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Pre Test and Post Test Means of Experimental and Control Group

S.No	Variables	Pre Test Mean	Post Test Mean
1	Speed	Exp: 7.05	Exp: 6.83
		Con: 7.05	Con: 7.04
2	Agility	Exp: 11.14	Exp:10.92
		Con: 11.14	Con: 11.12

Table 2: Computation of ‘t’ Ratio Between the Pre Test and Post Test Means of Speed of Experimental and Control Groups

Variables	Group	Mean diff	SD	σ DM	‘t’ ratio
Speed	Experimental	0.22	0.10	0.02	8.24*
	Control	0.01	0.05	0.01	1.00

* Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table 2 indicates that the obtained ‘t’ ratio was 8.24 on speed of experimental group was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The results of this study showed that 6 weeks practice of fartlek training produced a significant improvement in speed. Hence the formulated hypothesis related to this was accepted. The obtained ‘t’ ratio was 1.00 on speed of control group were found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant.

The mean scores of speed of experimental and control group were shown graphically in figure I.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Difference of Pre-Test and Post Test of Experimental and Control Group in Speed

Table 3: Computation of ‘t’ Ratio Between the Pre Test and Post Test Means of Agility of Experimental and Control Groups

Variables	Group	Mean Diff	SD	σ DM	‘t’ ratio
Agility	Experimental	0.21	0.10	0.02	8.45*
	Control	0.01	0.04	0.01	1.29

* Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table 3 indicates that the obtained ‘t’ ratio was 8.45 on agility of experimental group was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The results of this study showed that 6 weeks practice of fartlek training produced a significant improvement in agility. Hence the formulated hypothesis related to this was accepted. The obtained ‘t’ ratio was 1.29 on agility of control group were found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant. The mean scores of agility of experimental and control group were shown graphically in figure 2.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Difference of Pre-Test and Post Test of Experimental and Control Group in Agility

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement on selected physical variables.

References:

- Alves, J, M, V, M., Rebelo, A, N., Abrantes, C., and Sampaio, J. (2010). Short term effects of complex and contrast training in soccer players’ vertical jump, sprint, and agility abilities. *J Strength Cond Res*; 24(4): 936–941.

2. Antony, V. C. & R. Tomar (2019). Assessing the effect of fartlek training on perceived wellness of university students of saudiarabia: a randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 10(11), 5051-5056
3. Chad E. Smith., Brian Lyons & James C. Hannon (2014). A pilot study involving the effect of two different complex training protocols on lower body power. *Human Movement*, 15 (3), 141– 146.
4. Daniel, J., Jose, M., Gonzalez, R., & Fernando, N. (2009). Effects of complex vs non complex training programs on lower body maximum strength and power. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*. 17-4. 233-241.
5. Eduardo J. A. M. Santos & Manuel A. A. S. Janeira (2008). Effects of complex training on explosive strength in adolescent male basketball players. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*. 22,3.
6. Eduardo, J. A. M., Santos Manuel A. & Janeira, A. S. (2008). Effects of Complex Training on Explosive Strength in Adolescent Male Basketball Players. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*. 22(3)/903–909.
7. Elamaran M.A. & Muthu Eleckuvan R. (2014). Effect of fartlek training on selected physiological parameters among college male athletes. *International Journal of Physical Education, Fitness and Sports*. 3, 4, 2014.